

HOLISTIC APPROACH MADHUMEHA COMPLICATIONS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18796694>

How to cite this Article: ¹*Dr. Ram Raksha Shukla, ²Dr. Sanjeev M. Khuje, ³Dr. Om Prakash Dwivedi. (2026). Holistic Approach Madhumeha Complications. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(3), 65–66. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 28/01/2026

Article Revised on 18/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Madhumeha is a type of Vataja Prameha which closely resembles to chronic diabetes mellitus. In chronic phase of disease if adequate medical care is not administered, it may lead to complications and damage to body organs. Complications of diabetes are divided into two groups; Acute (immediate) and Chronic (late on set). This study paper includes the management of long term complication in Diabetic Patients. Persistent hyperglycemia damages blood vessels (vasculopathy), nerves (neuropathy), kidneys (nephropathy), eyes (retinopathy), and skin (wound healing disorders). Ayurvedic management of madhumeha complications involves a holistic approach combining Panchakarma therapies, Ayurvedic medicine, lifestyle changes and dietary modifications to manage neuropathy, retinopathy, nephropathy, wound healing disorders and cardiovascular issues.

KEYWORDS: Madhumeha, Prameha, chronic diabetes mellitus, Ayurvedic management.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is one of the fastest alarming global emergencies of the 21st century. Based on the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas 2021,^[1] it is estimated that 537 million people have diabetes; this number is expected to reach 643 million by 2030 and 783 million by 2045. In Ayurveda, the traditional system of medicine in India, diabetes mellitus can be considered as madhumeha, which is a subtype of Prameha, a condition characterized by sweet, astringent, dry, turbid, yellowish white coloured with frequent urination^[2] and systemic tissue degradation. Madhumeha closely resembles chronic diabetes mellitus, which is considered a maharoga (major systemic disease) with hereditary influences. Classical texts like Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita describe Prameha as a progressive disorder arising from faulty metabolism and excess vitiation of Kapha and Meda.^[3,4] The Systemic Impact of Diabetes, Kapha dominance leads to excess fluid retention and weight gain, causing insulin resistance. Kleda accumulation (moisture imbalance) destabilizes fat metabolism, increasing cholesterol, triglycerides, and inflammation. Agni dysfunction (digestive impairment) results in unmetabolized glucose accumulation, causing hyperglycemia. Vata aggravation

at later stages leads to micro vascular complications (neuropathy, retinopathy) and tissue degeneration.

Chronic (late on set) complications^[5] of Diabetes can lead to the development of multiple comorbidities, such as microvascular, macrovascular, and other complications. Microvascular complications in diabetes include neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy and diabetic foot. Macrovascular disease in diabetes is due to atherosclerosis, which leads to myocardial infarction, stroke, and peripheral arterial disease. Other complications are Skin and mouth problems: Increased susceptibility to bacterial and fungal infections, as well as gum disease. Hearing loss is more common in people with diabetes. Higher rates of depression and anxiety. Type 2 diabetes is associated with an increased risk of dementia, including Alzheimer's disease.

Management

Ayurvedic management of Madhumeha (diabetes mellitus) focuses on reducing Kapha, detoxifying the body, and strengthening digestion (Agni) to regulate metabolism effectively, through implementing Panchakarma therapies tailored to the complication. Panchakarma Purification and detoxification therapies

are considered highly effective in preventing long-term complications. The specific therapies depend on the patient's constitution and the imbalance of doshas. For Kapha-predominant patients (often associated with obesity) Vamana (emesis) is recommended, For Pitta-predominant patients Virechana (purgation) is advised.^[6,7,8,10,11] Udvartana (Herbal Powder Massage) stimulates fat metabolism, helping manage obesity-related diabetes. Other beneficial therapies include Shirolepa (head application), Moordha Taila (oil application on the head) and Tarpana (nourishing therapies). For specific complications: such as Diabetic neuropathy recent researches showed relief from tremors and numbness through a combination of Ayurvedic formulations and therapies. For Retinopathy: Anjana (collyrium) and Aschotana (eye drops) are mentioned as beneficial treatments. Cardiovascular Complications: Chronic hyperglycemia accelerates atherosclerosis, increasing the risk of heart attacks, strokes, and hypertension. Ayurveda describes Raktavaha Srotodushti (vascular damage) due to Pitta and Kapha imbalances. Nervous System Impairment: Diabetic neuropathy results in burning sensations, numbness, and autonomic dysfunction, aligning with Vata disorders affecting Majja Dhatu (nervous tissue). Ophthalmological Complications: patients suffering from diabetic retinopathy, cataracts, and glaucoma due to retinal microvascular damage, Ayurveda describes Pitta-Kapha vitiation in the eyes (Netra), requiring a combination of ocular therapies and systemic detoxification. Renal Dysfunction: Diabetic nephropathy, leading to proteinuria and kidney failure, is associated with Meda and Kleda accumulation, necessitating Rakta Shodhana (blood purification) therapies in Ayurveda.

Ayurvedic medicine For general management:^[12,13,14]

Herbs such as Guduchi, Dhatri, Nisha (turmeric), Shilajit, and Triphala are used for their Rasayana (rejuvenating) and balancing properties. Ayurvedic herbs have been extensively studied for their hypoglycemic, insulin-sensitizing, and anti-inflammatory effects. *Gymnema sylvestre* enhances insulin secretion and regenerates pancreatic beta cells. *Pterocarpus marsupium* has demonstrated blood sugar-lowering properties in clinical studies. Turmeric and Amla (*Emblica officinalis*) reduce oxidative stress and enhance glucose metabolism.

Lifestyle and dietary modifications Diet: Exercise: Engage in regular physical activity. Practicing yoga Managing stress is crucial for overall well-being and is addressed through techniques like meditation and specific yoga protocols. Practices like yoga, including specific asanas, Surya Namaskar, and Pranayama, are beneficial for improving metabolic and cardiovascular health. Focus on a low-glycemic diet, incorporating foods like bitter melon (Karavellaka), barley, and horse gram. Consume fruits like apples, oranges, and guava, while limiting high-sugar fruits such as chiku, mango and bananas. Avoid fatty and fried foods.

CONCLUSION

Chronic Diabetes mellitus (Madhumeah) is not just a disorder of glucose metabolism but a multisystem disease requiring a holistic approach, while modern medicine excels in blood sugar monitoring and pharmacological interventions. Ayurveda offers a deeper perspective by addressing root causes, improving digestion, and preventing complications through Panchakarma therapies, ayurvedic medicinal intervention, lifestyle and dietary modifications. These complications underscore diabetes requires a comprehensive and preventive Ayurvedic approach, not just glucose control.

REFERENCE

1. "Cho meter"IDF Diabetes Atlas: global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2017 and projections for 2045. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.*, 2018; 138: 271-81.
2. Charak samhita nidan 4/44 By Agnivesha; Translated into English by Dr. Ram Karan & Vaidya Bhagwan Das; Chaukamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi & Krishnadas Academy, 2001.
3. Madhava Nidanam; Madhavakara, Translated into English by Dr. K. R. Srikantha Murthy; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Krishnadas Academy, 1987; Chapter - 33; Page No.- 116, 119; Sloka - Referred -20-36; Roga Vinischayam.
4. Ashtanga Hridayam- Nidanasthanam; Vagbhata, Translated into English by Dr. K.R. Srikantha Murthy; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Krishnadas Academy, 1992; II(10): 92-99. Prameha - Sankya, Nidana, Rupas, Samanya Lakshanas, Upadravas etc.
5. Davidson's Clinical Medicine: Edited by John Macleod; 1984, Reprint - 1985, 1986; Chapter - 12- Endocrine & Metabolic Diseases; 457-465; Diabetes Mellitus.
6. Charaka Chikitsa sthanam; By Agnivesha; Translated into English by Dr. Ram Karan & Vaidya Bhagwan Das; Chaukamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi & Krishnadas Academy, 2001.
7. Sushruta Samhita: By Kaviraj Kunjalal Bhashagraha; Chaukamba Sanskrit Series, Varanasi, 1963; II(13): 286-391. The Medical treatment of Madhumeah.
8. Ashtanga Hridayam- Chikitsa sthanam; Vagbhata, Translated into English by Dr. K.R. Srikantha Murthy; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Krishnadas Academy; Section - 4; Chapter - 12; 383-390; Chikitsa.
9. P.V. Sharma Dravyaguna Vijnana - Part -II; Chaukamba Vidya bhavan, Chowk, Banaras, 1956.
10. A. Practical hand book of Panchakarma Procedures - CCRAS 2009: Chapter - Vamana; Page - 17; Chapter - Virechana; Page - 21; Slokas - Astanga Hridaya Sutrasthana - 18 - 1,2; 8,9.
11. The Principles and Practice of Kaya Chikitsa: Dr. S. Suresh Babu; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Krishnadas Academy, 2007; III: 100-109. Endocrine Diseases and Medicines.

12. Basavarajeeyam – 9th Chapter, 433.
13. A Text book of Kayachikitsa: Dr. Subhash Rande and Dr. Sunanda Ranade; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Krishnadas Academy; Chapter – 4 - Medovaha Srotas – Prameha, 441-451; Prameha
14. Bhavaprakash: Bhavamishra; Chaukamba Oriental Publisher & Distributor, Varanasi; Volume - II, Chapter – 38; 484, 497, 498; Sloka - Referred 107; Medicines.